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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND INVITRO EVALUATION OF
CONTROLLED RELEASE TABLETS OF PROPRANOLOL
HCL AND MIGLITOL****Ramavath Aruna*, Shafiya Fatima, Mohammed Ibrahim, Swetha Reddy, Ayesha
Qureshi, Farheen Naaz, Shaik Ejas, Imaduddin.MD**

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Article Received: June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Propranolol hydrochloride is used to treat high blood pressure, thyrotoxicosis, capillary hemangiomas, performance anxiety, and essential tremors and used to prevent migraine headaches and Miglitol acts by inhibiting the ability of the patient to break down complex carbohydrates into glucose. It is primarily used in diabetes mellitus type 2 for establishing greater glycemic control by preventing the digestion of carbohydrates. In this investigation-controlled release tablet of Propranolol Hcl and Miglitol were prepared using different polymers such as xanthum gum, tragacanth, sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, HPMC K4M, Eudragit S100, ethyl cellulose by direct compression method. All the pre-compression and post compression parameters of designed formulations of F₁, F₈ were evaluated and found to be within permissible limit. The optimized formulation (F₇) showed maximum percentage of drug release (100%) within in 6hrs when compared to other formulations. From the FT-IR and DSC evaluation study it was concluded that there was no possible drug and polymer interactions. The short-term stability studies were carried out at 40±2°C and 75±5% RH and were confirmed about no changes in the weight, hardness and friability. Based on study results it may be concluded that tablets prepared will emerge as eminent candidate in treatment of hypertension and diabetes.

Key Words: Propranolol Hcl, Miglitol, controlled release tablet, Eudragit S100, sodium cross carmallose, Ethyl cellulose, Tragacanth, HPMC K4M.

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INTRODUCTION:

Among all the routes of administration, oral route of administration is very convenient and safe way to deliver a drug into the systemic circulation¹. The term Controlled release drug delivery (CRDD) formulations are used to achieve or extend therapeutic action by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time only after administration of single dose². The oral controlled release system is usually made of polymers, and the mechanism of drug release is generally regulated by diffusion controlled release, dissolution controlled release, ion exchange resins, osmotically controlled release, enteric coated (pH dependent system) and altered density formulation (or) Bouyant systems^{3, 4}. An ideal dosage regimen of drug delivery is one that provides a continuous delivery of drugs by rapidly attaining the required plasma concentration. The time interval of drug administration is mainly depending on the biological half-life of the drug. The main advantages of CRDDS is it improves patient compliance mainly with long-term treatments for chronic diseases, removes fluctuation in plasma drug concentration, reduces dose and dosing time intervals and this type of delivery system is suitable for drugs which are having short biological half-life, and therefore eliminates the drug rapidly from the body⁵.

For the development of CRDDS polymers such as Xanthum, Gum Tragacanth, Eudragit S 100, HPMC K4M, etc are used. An ideal CRDDS is the one, which releases the drug at predetermined rate, locally or systematically for a specific period of time^{6, 7}. Propranolol Hydrochloride and Miglitol was formulated as an oral controlled release dosage form using various polymers like Xanthum gum,

Tragacanth, Sodium Carboxy Methyl Cellulose, HPMC K4M, Eudragit S100, and Ethyl Cellulose by direct compression method. Propranolol is a prototype, non-selective β_1/β_2 adrenoceptor antagonist and doesn't possess other autonomic nervous system activity. It is widely used in the treatment of hypertension, migraine, angina pectoris, cardiac arrhythmias and many other cardiovascular disorders. It is highly lipophilic drug exhibits marked central actions like anxiolytic, anti-aggressive and anti-psychotic effects⁸. Miglitol is a derivative of nojirimycin⁹. It is a complex oligosaccharide reversible inhibits α -glucosidase. It is more potent in inhibiting sucrase¹⁰.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials: Propranolol Hydrochloride, Miglitol, Xanthum, HPMC K4M, Eudragit S100 and Ethyl Cellulose were obtained from Synthetic Syndicate, Mumbai. Tragacanth, Sodium CMC, Magnesium stearate, Micro crystalline cellulose, Talc and PVP K30 are obtained from EsseL Fine chem, Mumbai.

Methods:**Technique used for Preparation of Tablets:**

Direct Compression Method was used for the preparation of tablets. Take 45mg (15%) of polymer in a motor. Weigh accurate quantity of API i.e., Propranolol hydrochloride (40mg) and Miglitol (25mg), add to the above polymer. Mix thoroughly with the help of pestle. Add 12mg of PVP K 30 to the above blend and mix it properly. Add Talc and Magnesium stearate. Make up the volume to 300mg with MCC (Micro crystalline cellulose) and mix it uniformly. Finally the powder is subjected for compression **Table 1**.

TABLE 1: Formulation Of Propranolol Hcl And Miglitol Controlled Release Tablets.

INGREDIENTS	F1(mg)	F2(mg)	F3(mg)	F4(mg)	F5(mg)	F6(mg)	F7(mg)	F8(mg)
Propranolol Hcl	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Miglitol	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Xanthum	45	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gum Tragacanth	-	45	-	-	-	-	-	-
HPMC K4M	-	-	45	-	-	-	-	-
Sodium CMC	-	-	-	45	-	-	30	30
Eudrajit S100	-	-	-	-	45	-	45	-
Ethyl Cellulose	-	-	-	-	-	45	-	45
PVP K 30	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Mg.Sterate	06	06	06	06	06	06	06	06
Talc	06	06	06	06	06	06	06	06
MCC	166	166	166	166	166	166	136	136

Pre-Compression Evaluation:

Angle of Repose (θ): The frictional forces in a loose powder or granules can be measured by the angle of repose. This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of powder or granules and the horizontal plane $1B^{11}$. $\theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$ Where, θ is the angle of repose, h is the height, r is the radius.

Bulk density: Bulk density is determined by pouring gently 25gms of sample through a glass funnel into a 100ml graduated cylinder. The volume occupied by the sample was recorded. Bulk density was calculated as

$$\text{Bulk density (g/ml)} = \frac{\text{weight of sample}}{\text{volume occupied by the sample}}$$

Tapped density: The tapped density was determined by pouring 25gm sample through a glass funnel into a 100ml graduated cylinder. The cylinder was tapped from height of 2 inches until a constant volume was obtained. Volume occupied by the sample after tapping was recorded and tapped density was calculated as $Tap = M/V$. Where, Tap = Tapped density; M = Weight of sample; V = Tapped volume of powder.

Compressibility (%): It is also one of the simple methods to evaluate flow property of the powder. It is determined from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flowable it is. As such, it is measures of the relative importance of inter particulate interactions. In a free-flowing powder, such interactions are generally less significant, and the bulk and tapped densities will be closer in value. For poorer flowing materials, there are frequently greater inter particle interactions, and a greater difference between the bulk and tapped densities will be observed. These differences are reflected in the Compressibility Index which is calculated using the following formula $Carr's Index = \left[\left(\frac{Tap - b}{Tap} \right) \right] \times 100$; Where, Tap = Tapped Density; b = Bulk Density.¹²

Hausner ratio: It provides an indication of the degree of densification which could result from vibration of feed hopper. $Hausner ratio = \frac{Tapped Density}{Bulk Density}$ ¹³

Evaluation of Controlled Release Tablets^{14; 15}

Weight variation test: To study the weight variation, twenty tablets were taken and their weight was determined individually and collectively on a digital weighing balance. The average weight of one tablet was determined from the collective weight. The weight variation test would be a satisfactory method of determining the drug content uniformity. Not more than two of the individual weights deviate

from the average weight by more than the percentage shown in the following table and none deviate by more than twice the percentage. The mean and deviation were determined. The % deviation was calculated using the following formula $\% Deviation = \left(\frac{Individual weight - Average Weight}{Average Weight} \right) \times 100$

Friability: It is measured of mechanical strength of tablets. Roche friabilator was used to determine the friability by following procedure. Pre weighed tablets were placed in the friabilator. The tablets were rotated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes (100 rotations). At the end of test, the tablets were re weighed, loss in the weight of tablet is the measure of friability and is expressed in percentage as $\% Friability = \left[\frac{W1 - W2}{W1} \right] \times 100$ Where, $W1$ = Initial weight of three tablets; $W2$ = Weight of the three tablets after testing.

Hardness: Hardness of tablet is defined as the force applied across the diameter of the tablet in order to break the tablet. The resistance of the tablet to chipping, abrasion or breakage under condition of storage transformation and handling before usage depends on its hardness. For each formulation, the hardness of three tablets was determined using Monsanto hardness tester and the average is calculated and presented with deviation.

Thickness: Tablet thickness is an important characteristic in reproducing appearance. Tablet thickness is an important characteristic in reproducing appearance. Average thickness for core and coated tablets is calculated and presented with deviation.

Drug Content: Ten tablets from each formulation batch were powdered and a quantity of the powder equivalent to one tablet weight were accurately weighed, transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask containing few ml of 6.8pH buffer and were allowed to stand to ensure complete solubility of the drug. The solution was suitably diluted and the absorption was determined by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 244nm and also at 291nm. The drug concentration was calculated from the calibration curve. For controlled layer drug content was done in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

In-vitro disintegration time: The tablet was placed in each tube, and the basket rack was positioned in a 100ml beaker of Sorenson's buffer (pH 6.8) at $37^\circ C \pm 2^\circ C$. The time required for complete disintegration of tablet was noted.

In-vitro drug release studies of tablets: In-vitro dissolution studies of all formulations (F1-F8) were

evaluated by using USP dissolution apparatus-Type-II (Paddle method), Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as dissolution medium, 900 ml of dissolution fluid was used at temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Sample size is Equivalent to 5mg. Samples of 5ml were withdrawn at regular time intervals of 30mins, 1,2,3,4,5 & 6hrs by using 5ml of Pipette. The volume withdrawn was replaced by fresh volume of dissolution medium to maintain constant of medium. The filtered samples were analysed spectro-photometrically at 291nm. The amount of drug released was determined using respective calibration curves. Dissolution studies for each formulation were performed in triplicates.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR): The FT-IR spectra were obtained using FT-IR spectrometer. The samples were previously ground and mixed thoroughly with potassium bromide, an infrared transparent matrix in 1:5 (sample: KBr) ratio, respectively. The KBr discs were prepared by compressing the powders at a pressure of 5 tons for 5min in a hydraulic press. Forty-five scans were obtained at a resolution of 4cm^{-1} from 4500 to 400cm^{-1} .¹⁶

Differential Scanning Calorimetry: The DSC measurements were performed on a Pyris Diamond TG/DTA differential scanning calorimeter with thermal analyzer. All accurately weighed samples (about 5mg) were placed in sealed aluminium pans. An empty aluminium pan was used as reference¹⁷.

Stability studies as per ICH guidelines: Stability of a drug has been defined as the ability of a particular formulation, in a specific container, to remain within its physical, chemical, therapeutic and toxicological specifications. In any rational design and evaluation of dosage forms for drugs, stability of the active component must be a major criterion in determining their acceptance or rejection¹⁸.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Determination of λ_{max} of Miglitol and Propranolol Hcl: Miglitol and Propranolol Hcl was scanned in the respective medium of pH 3.2 acetate buffer and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer for its absorption maxima and was found that Miglitol and Propranolol exhibited maximum absorption at 244.0 nm and 291 nm respectively. Calibration curve was developed with concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, $10\mu\text{g/mL}$ the best fit line R^2 was found to be 0.9999.

Organoleptic properties: Organoleptic properties such as physical appearance and sieve analysis were evaluated and the results are within the standards. The drug is showing solubility in methanol and in water. The characterization features like moisture content, LOD, Melting Point, BD, and TD were evaluated and the results are within the standards.

Pre-compression parameters of mini tablets: In this study, the method employed for tableting was direct compression for which the drug, excipients and polymers should possess good flow properties. Pre-compression parameters were studied for the flow properties of powder blend, to achieve constant uniformity of tablet weight.

Bulk density, tapped density, Hausner ratio, Compressibility index: Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has excellent flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.39 to 0.46 (gm/ml) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.46 to 0.63 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of the F2,F3 and F7 formulations was found to be below 18 which shows that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations have shown the hausner's ratio below 1.3 indicating the powder has good flow properties. The pre-compression parameters values are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2: Physical Properties Of Drug Excipients Mixtures:

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/mL)	Tapped density (gm/mL)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	17.2	0.41	0.52	21.1	1.26
F2	18.2	0.40	0.46	13.0	1.15
F3	16.6	0.41	0.48	14.5	1.17
F4	18.7	0.40	0.51	21.6	1.2
F5	19.2	0.46	0.63	22.9	1.36
F6	23.2	0.39	0.50	22	1.28
F7	27.4	0.45	0.57	13	1.26
F8	34.2	0.40	0.52	23	1.3

Post compression parameters of mini tablets

Organoleptic properties: All the mini tablets show similar colour, odour, taste and physical appearance. There is no impact of different in their organoleptic properties.

Hardness test: By using the different excipients, the hardness values ranged from 4.5-5.5 kg/cm² for formulations (F1-F8).

Weight variation test: The entire tablet passes weight variation test, as the average % weight variation was within the Pharmacopeial limit - 7.5%. It was found to be 298.6mg – 305.6 mg. The weight of all the tablets was found to be uniform with less deviation.

Drug content uniformity: The concentration of the drug in all the formulations with different polymers was found to be 97.3 – 100.6%. It was within the IP limits. The results are shown in the **Table 3**.

TABLE 3: Quality Control Parameters for Tablets:

Formulation codes	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
F1	299.8±1.48	5.4 ±0.44	0.36	4.08±0.17	100.6
F2	300.4±0.54	4.5±0.31	0.39	3.70±0.25	100.2
F3	298.6±0.41	5.5±0.40	0.43	3.81±0.80	99.8
F4	300.8±1.64	5.5±0.55	0.12	4.2±0.20	99.4
F5	305.6±1.14	4.6±0.57	0.54	4.08±0.66	98.9
F6	299.2±0.83	5.0±0.30	0.58	3.91±0.25	99.4
F7	299.9±0.67	4.5±0.57	0.64	4.1±0.71	99.3
F8	299.0±0.43	5.4±0.60	0.37	4.0±0.89	98.9

In-vitro drug release studies of tablets: In-vitro drug release studies of all formulations (F1-F8) were evaluated. The results are shown in the **Table 4 and Table 5**.

TABLE 4: In-Vitro Drug Release Studies:

Time in min	F1		F2		F3		F4	
	MIG	PRO	MIG	PRO	MIG	PRO	MIG	PRO
30	13.36	8.60	20.0	11.86	15.78	9.80	25.0	14.81
1hr	25.60	17.91	33.14	28.62	28.89	19.76	48.71	32.40
2hr	33.38	21.71	50.31	40.18	38.90	30.32	56.61	43.31
6.8pH buffer								
3 hr	56.67	68.84	68.76	63.15	67.72	43.40	70.68	64.32
4 hr	99.89	98.80	100.04	99.46	82.0	77.49	86.60	87.70
6 hr	-	-	-	-	98.3	100.1	98.5	99.8
8 hr	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

TABLE 5: In-Vitro Drug Release Studies:

Time in min	F5		F6		F7		F8	
	MIG	PRO	MIG	PRO	MIG	PRO	MIG	PRO
30	13.36	8.60	20.0	11.86	15.78	9.80	25.0	14.81
1hr	25.60	17.91	33.14	28.62	28.89	19.76	48.71	32.40
2hr	33.38	21.71	50.31	40.18	38.90	30.32	56.61	43.31
6.8pH buffer								
3 hr	56.67	38.84	68.76	63.15	67.72	43.40	70.68	64.32
4 hr	79.89	68.80	80.04	79.46	82.0	77.49	86.60	87.70
6 hr	99.6	98.7	100.6	99.9	91.5	90.2	100.1	99.6
8 hr	-	-	-	-	100.8	100.1	-	-

***In-vitro* Dissolution studies:**

Dissolution is carried out in USP apparatus type-2 apparatus at 50rpm in 900ml dissolution media for 2 hours in 3.2 acetate buffer. This was followed by dissolution in 900ml of 6.8 pH phosphate buffers in USP Apparatus 2. This was rotated at a speed of 50 rpm, and a temperature of $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, for 360 minutes. Based upon the dissolution profile the F7 formulation was optimized as it suits the extended release nature and comparable with the release of other formulations. The dissolution data of Miglitol and Propranolol Hcl results are shown in the (Fig 1a.&1b).

FIG 1A: Dissolution profile for formulation F1 to F4, FIG 1B: Dissolution profile for formulation F5 to F8

FTIR spectral data: The FT-IR represents the peaks of the Miglitol and propranolol functional groups. These peaks were not affected, they were prominently observed in IR-spectra of Miglitol and propranolol along with other excipients. There was no difference in the position of the absorption bands, hence providing evidence for the absence of any chemical incompatibility between pure drugs with the excipients. The results of Drug – Excipient Compatibility Studies by FT-IR were shown below. (Fig 2, 3 & 4)

FIG 2: FT-IR spectra of Propranolol HCl

FIG 3: FT-IR spectra of Miglitol.

FIG 4: FT-IR spectra of Optimised Formulation

DSC: The DSC represents the melting points of the Miglitol and propranolol. These peaks were not affected, they were prominently observed in DSC graph of Miglitol and propranolol along with other excipients. There was no difference in the position of the melting point, hence providing evidence for the absence of any chemical incompatibility between pure drugs with the excipients. The results of drug by Differential Scanning Calorimetry were shown below in Fig 5, 6A & 6B.

FIG 5: DSC of Propranolol

FIG 6A: DSC of Miglitol, FIG 6B: DSC of Optimised Formulation

Stability studies: From the stability study of promising formulation F₇, it was shown that there were no physical appearance changes, but slight decrease in %drug content was seen at 30 days of stability studies. But hardness, friability melting time decrease from 1 day to 30 days but all was within the limits only. The results were shown in table 6.

TABLE 6: STABILITY STUDIES PARAMETERS OF OPTIMISED FORMULATION.

Parameters Evaluated	1 ST Day	30 Days
Appearance	White	No change
%Drug content	99.3	99.0
Hardness (kg/sq.in)	4.5±0.57	4.5±0.57
%Friability	0.64	0.63

CONCLUSION:

The monolithic controlled release tablets containing Miglitol and propranolol were successfully prepared by direct compression method. Various formulations were prepared and evaluated with an aim of presenting Miglitol and propranolol as controlled release for improving the patient's compliance. The physiochemical evaluation results for the granules of all trials pass the official limits in angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Hausner ratio and compressibility index. The prepared blend for controlled release tablets were also maintained the physiochemical properties of tablets such as thickness, hardness, weight variation, friability and drug content. The optimized formulation F7 from total formulations contains the average thickness of 2.4mm, average hardness of 4.5 kg/cm², average weight of 299mg, friability of 0.64%. The F7 formulation which releases the Miglitol and propranolol in controlled manner in 1st hour it releases 15.78 and 9.80 % respectively, but the remaining drug release was sustained up to 8 hours. Hence it may be summarized that the tablets prepared by direct compression method for controlled release tablet might be a perfect and effective formulation in treatment of hypertension and diabetes.

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